

The Nitration of Coumarin.

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During the nitration of coumarin, by the method described by Morgan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1233), there was obtained a yellowish, crystalline material which melted indefinitely from 130° to 170°. Attempts were made to isolate a new nitro-derivative from this material but without success. Repeated fractional crystallisation from acetic acid and other solvents led generally to a product melting sharply at 140-141°. This is now found to be a mixture of 6-nitro-coumarin, and another mono-nitrocoumarin.

Each of these nitrocoumarins dissolves in an alkaline solution with the formation of nitro-coumarinates. The free coumarinic acids differ in stability: that derived from 6-nitrocoumarin readily reverts to that substance whilst the other is stable in comparison. A separation was effected on this basis.

On repeatedly dissolving the coumarinic acids in bicarbonate of soda, and fractionally precipitating with dilute acid, an acid was obtained, which, on rapid heating, melted with sudden decomposition at 149°, and gave, on boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid, a nitro-coumarin melting sharply at 187°. On oxidation with permanganate in alkaline solution, it gave 3-nitro-salicylic acid (m.p. 126°) in good quantity, the product being thereby identified with 8-nitro-coumarin (Miller and Kinkelin, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1701).

The direct nitration of coumarin was hitherto supposed to result in the formation of only the 6-nitro-derivative which, on protracted treatment with nitric acid, yielded the 3:6-dinitro- and finally the 3:6:8-trinitro-coumarin. It is now proved that 8-nitro-coumarin, prepared previously by the indirect process from 8-nitro-salicylaldehyde, is also a product of the direct nitration of coumarin and forms approximately 7 per cent. of the total.

The phenomenon of a mixture of two different substances melting sharply appearing to be extraordinary; the melting points of different mixtures of 6-nitro- and 8-nitro-coumarin were observed. It was found that the mixture in equal amounts melted sharply at 140-141° whilst other mixtures had melted indefinitely.

The product obtained from the residues, melting at 140-141° appears, therefore, to be an equimolecular mixture of the 6-nitro- and 8-nitro-coumarins.

EXPERIMENTAL.

8-Nitro-coumarin.

Coumarin (20 g.) was nitrated in the usual way (Morgan, *loc. cit.*), the acetic acid filtrate thrown into water, and the precipitate collected and washed (6 g.). It was then heated with two per cent. sodium hydroxide solution till the whole of it went into solution with a deep orange-red colour, and cooled to 80°. Very dilute hydrochloric acid was added until the solution was faintly acidic. The bulky yellow precipitate was allowed to stand for about 15 minutes and then collected. (The filtrate, after a short time, gave a quantity of needle-like crystals which were identified as those of 6-nitro-coumarin). The yellow precipitate was kept on porous tile for two hours, and then shaken up with water and excess of sodium bicarbonate. The mixture was filtered. A considerable amount of solid was obtained which proved to be 6-nitro-coumarin. The filtrate was acidified, the coumarinic acids were separated and dried for two hours and dissolved again in sodium bicarbonate solution. This process of dissolution in bicarbonate and acidification was repeated (usually six times) until the filtrate from the coumarinic acid gave no crystals on standing even for a day. The yellow acid thus obtained when dried, melted with decomposition at 149° if the bath was rapidly heated, and dissolved completely in cold sodium bicarbonate solution even after leaving it on the porous tile for two days. On warming this acid with 4N-hydrochloric acid, a nitro-coumarin, melting at 187°, was obtained. A mixture of this with 6-nitro-coumarin melted indefinitely at 139°-141°.

Oxidation.

The nitro-coumarin obtained above (0.5 g.) was dissolved in 2N-sodium hydroxide (25 c.c.) cooled to 0°, and a 1 per cent. solution of permanganate slowly added. The mixture was finally heated on the water-bath for an hour, the solution filtered from the precipitated manganese dioxide, concentrated on the water-bath to a small bulk and acidified with strong hydrochloric acid. Colourless

needles (0.3 g.) separated, m.p. 125-126°, either alone, or mixed with 8-nitro-salicylic acid.

Melting Point of a Mixture of 6-Nitro- and 8-Nitro-coumarin.

The required amounts of the two substances were weighed into an agate mortar, intimately mixed, and the melting point of each mixture was observed thrice.

6-Nitrocoumarin (in gm.)	8-Nitrocoumarin (in gm.)	Approximate temperatures between which complete melting takes place.
1	0.25	138°-175°
	0.50	139°-170°
1	0.75	139°-155°
1	1.00	140°-141°
1	1.25	139°-160°
1	1.50	139°-160°
1	1.75	138°-165°
1	2.00	138°-170°

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